

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18282099

Influence Of Motivation On Teachers' Performance And Job Satisfaction In Public Secondary Schools Within Edo South Senatorial District In Edo State

Banke Margaret AKINWUMI¹; Chika Catherine ONYENEKE (PhD)² & Tederhi OMWIRHIREN³

^{1,3}Federal College of Education (Technical) Ekiadolor, Benin-City, Edo State, Nigeria

¹E-mail:bankeakinwumi97@gmail.com; ³E-mail:Ted4real2010@gmail.com

²University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria

E-mail: chitochionyeneke@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Motivation which can either be intrinsic or extrinsic is a drive that pushes people to move toward accomplishing a goal and plays significant role in advancing the quality of teaching and learning processes. This study identified motivational factors that can influence teachers' job performance such as good salary structure, proper recognition, professional development and working in conducive environment and established relationship between motivation and teachers' performance. The study suggested that in order to make teachers remain in the service of the state, good salary structure should be prepared and paid to them alongside other benefits which their counterparts from various disciplines are enjoying, they should be encouraged to always further their academic careers and be trained in the utilization of modern technological instructional materials, also conducive working environment for learning and teaching with relevant instructional materials should be provided to enhance performance.

Keywords: Motivation, Teachers, Performance, Satisfaction, Public Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction among teachers in government owe secondary schools is fundamental to how they perform their assigned duties. It is the fulfillment derives from ones' job, it is a function of how ones desires, needs and aspiration are met through the job. It is an important component for increased productivity and involvement of employee in any organization. It is a mental response and reward that employee experience directly. A lot of factors can lead to job satisfaction among employee and have great impact on their productivity and efficiency. When a worker is satisfied with his/her job, it make such to develop positive attitude towards the job, encourages such person to work with great vigour, which will lead to great achievement and good performance, and in teaching profession it also leads to retention of teachers, hence overcome the problem associated with lack of teachers in schools. Teachers' job performance is dependent on their satisfactions. Teachers' performance can be assessed based on how punctual they are to work, eager to be at work, quick and prompt response to duties, total commitment to work, effective teaching, and regular evaluation of students' performance.

Teaching is a profession which a lot of people downplay because of the way and manner the society view the profession and also the statues of teacher compare to other professions like Medical doctors, Banker, Engineers etc. Teachers play a vital role in building a nation's future as such it imperative to ensure that

they are comfortable and derive pleasure in discharging their duties. Satisfied employees will be more effective in ensuring that the mandate of the organization is achieved.

Motivation can be defined as internal drive that pushes individual to perform, it is one of the most vital factors that move one to realize his or her set goals, Mbwana (2015). Motivation contains both intrinsic (internal) and extrinsic (external) factors which serves as driven force to enable one to be committed and developed an explicit desires towards ones job. Intrinsic motivation arises from inside the individual. It comes when one has personal satisfaction in what he is engaging in. Extrinsic motivation refers to motivation that arises from sources outside the individual. It is the incentive that drives an individual's behaviour towards a goal.

In achieving the goals and objectives of schools, teachers' motivation has been seen as key factor, if teachers are motivated, they will influence the educational system positively through effective commitment to performing their tasks which is based on job satisfaction, Igbafe and Ogonor (2019). Teacher motivation is the driving force that influences their willingness and commitment to their work. Teacher derived intrinsic motivation from internal satisfaction gained from the teaching process which include pleasure of teaching, sense of fulfillment, and a desire to make a constructive impact on learners. They can be motivated extrinsically through their salaries, being recognized, given opportunities for professional development and having a conducive working environment. Motivated teachers are more likely to find their work fulfilling, feel a sense of accomplishment, put in extra effort, be creative in their teaching, and persist through challenges. These will automatically lead to higher job satisfaction which enviably leads to improved instructional practices and student learning outcomes. Therefore, despite the challenges facing the status of teacher, if they are being motivated, it could lead to job satisfactions and finally enhance better performance on their parts.

Teacher motivation is of great significant as it improves the skills and knowledge of teachers and has direct influence on the student's achievement, Mustafa and Othman (2010). If teachers are not well motivated, it will affect their competency which directly influence the students and the educational system. In Nigeria, teaching profession was previously accorded with respect, honor and dignity, it was seen as an enviable profession, a lot of people were willing to associate and join the profession. Unfortunately, government neglects the educational sector and teachers were dissatisfied with their working environment, salary structure, among others. According to Ogbonna (2014), teachers' motivation is essential in order to improve their job satisfaction and performance. Ogbonna further suggests that teachers put in their best when they are given incentives and are getting satisfaction in their jobs and are made to feel that their interests are considered. According to him, if teachers are to be retained so as to improve students' performance, it is important that they are properly motivated from time to time so that they equally feel satisfied with their job.

There is an extensive view of people about teacher motivation worldwide, it appears that there is a great concern that most of the teachers working in public schools are poorly motivated due to mishmash of low morale and job satisfactory, poor leadership, improper provision and capturing of teachers welfare in government budget, poor incentive, inadequate instructional/teaching facilities, and therefore, need to improve the welfare of teachers as professionals. Nadeem et al. (2011) stated that economic and social conditions of teachers have effect on their performance. Factors such as lack of facilities, low salary, status of teachers in society, teachers mental health and morale, stress of work, relation with staff and head teachers, working environment have great impact on female teachers' performance. When there is a poor economic and social condition in the place where the school is located, the level of motivation of teachers reduces. They therefore concluded that there is a significant relationship between these factors of motivation and the efficiency of female teachers. According to Brandmiller et al. (2020), teacher's performance will be at its highest level in carrying out their responsibilities if motivation is maintained. The way people react to their working environment determines their basis. Whichever way it is being viewed, work motivation has an important influence on the performance of teachers. Rofifah et al. (2021). It has been observed that teachers who are intrinsically motivated focus on the benefits of activities related directly to teaching and place more emphasize on the internal satisfaction they derive from their work. Meanwhile, teachers who are extrinsically driven focus more and are interested in other benefits

such as income, and other extrinsic rewards accompanying their profession. Mary (2010) revealed the influence of intrinsic motivation on job performance of teachers. The findings revealed a significant positive association between intrinsic motivation and teachers' job performance, meaning that an intrinsic motivation is dependent on teachers' job performance. Shaikh et al. (2019) in their research discovered that all external factors that is extrinsic rewards positively and significantly have great impact on employees. This work offers wide-range of information on the significance of external issues in revealing workers' job performance. According Tasya and Gilang (2020), motivation is seen to have significant impact of employees' performance. The major stakeholder in the development of any society is teacher, without their involvement the society will remain illiterate thereby limiting its development. Nurun Nabi et al. (2017) discovered that if workers are well motivated, their efficiency and effectiveness will improve significantly in order to achieve the goals of the organization. Therefore, for educational goals to be achieved optimally, teachers' motivation is very imperative.

Theoretical Framework

The content theory of motivation deals with what motivates people and it is concerned with individual needs and goals. Some psychologists such as Abraham Maslow, Frederick Herzberg, David McClelland studied motivation from a "content" perspective. Hence, theoretical framework of this research work is based on their theories. The Needs-based theories of motivation are founded on the belief that an individual's behaviours is motivated by actions that satisfy their needs and wants. For an establishment and its employees to succeed in meeting its organizational goals, an employer must find a way to motivate each team member. Various techniques must be adopted by the Managers to ensure that their employees stay motivated and thereby productive. David McClelland for instance developed the theory which categorized people's need within the organization into three known as motivational needs which include need for affiliation, achievement and power. Need for affiliation was connected with workers at the lower level of the organizational hierarchy and meant that people need meaningful relationship and places of work are considered to create an avenue for works to build a good relationship among themselves. Need for achievement was connected with middle-level workers and entails workers craving to be seen as achieving more to his/her organization. Need for power was connected with the top management and he discovered that workers at this particular level are usually driven by strong desire to change the course of events or make strong impression on others and events, therefore, want to be in control of situations and people. Relating achievement theory to present study, the researcher stated that motivation played a substantial role in influencing the performance of teachers as all the study variables; teacher' in- service training, teachers' promotion, and the working environment, was basically seen as a motivation with significant influence on teachers' job performance. In order to increase teachers' job performance in public secondary schools, teachers at every level in the hierarchy of the school administration must be made to feel that their needs are catered for in order to get motivated for higher performance. Management should know that workers must to be treated according to their needs instead of being treated collectively in order to enhance their performance.

Expectancy theory of motivation which was proposed and developed in 1964 by Victor Vroom focuses on and stresses outcomes rather than needs. The expectancy theory states that people's intensity of work effort will depend on their perception that their effort will result in the desired outcome Junhao (2023). This means that people will work harder when they believe that their extra efforts will improve their performance and result in rewards. This statement suggests that teachers' performance can be enhanced through motivation, if teachers' expectations of rewards are low, they tend to leave the profession and look for an alternative means of survival that can meet their respective needs. The theory also help to understand that teachers can work hard in order to achieve the excepted teaching and learning outcome, hence their efforts and abilities can lead to better job performance and satisfaction.

Good Salary Structure on Teachers' job performance and satisfaction

Education is one of the most potent tools needed by a nation to reduce the level of poverty and inequality among its citizens as well as improving their health and general well-being. It is used to lay the

foundation for a sustainable growth and development of the society. Therefore, the rate of development in any society is tied to well-structured, managed and supervised educational system. Education as an instrument for national growth has changed the globe into a universal community through the innovation from Science and Technology, FRN, 2013. Education is regarded globally, as a reliable instrument for the achievements of national goals. It is important for the development of every nation, and to a great extent, determines the possible pattern of the other sectors while at the same time providing an insight into the nation's future, National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2009). The effectiveness of education in a particular nations depends primarily on the teachers' job performance and the subsequent impact measured by students' achievement.

Generally, people work to earn money so as to meet their personal and domestic needs. If what they do could not cater for these needs, they will not be satisfy doing it and it will affect their commitment and hence poor performance. Therefore, teachers' salary will greatly influence their performance and job satisfaction. Bell (2012) hypothesized that, of all conditions of service, salary is the best determinant of teachers' job performance and productivity. For teachers to perform well and be satisfied with their jobs their salaries must be attractive. Comparing teachers' salaries with their counterpart in other professional fields like medicine, banking etc having the same qualification and experience, it can be said that they are not well paid. Thus, difficult for them to meet their basic necessities of life and constantly looking for other alternative to meet these needs which will invariably affect their effective and efficient performance. Jobs that offer higher salary would automatically attract more and better qualifies personnel than anyone that offers a lower pay, Adamu and Garba (2019). High salaries give workers a sense of accomplishment apart from the task before them. Nevertheless, this may differ according to the type of job satisfaction examine. A teacher with high salary may still be dissatisfied when he spends several hours at work at the detriment of his health and family needs, Schaefer (2005). Several studies that were carried out in Nigeria showed low job satisfaction as well as low morale amongst Nigerian teachers (Kayode, 2012; Businge, 2011). This has led to job dissatisfaction and low performance of teacher as such National Union of Teachers (NUT) has continued maintained that the government should develop a good salary structure and reward system to promote teachers' job satisfaction Komolafe (2010).

Influence of Proper recognition on Teachers' job performance and satisfaction

Recognition is one of the needs that influence teachers' motivation to teach effectively. This need relates to the desire for appreciation by the society and the government for the role they play in nurturing learners to the expectations of the society. An important strategy for creating enthusiasm among teachers is to appreciate their performance and their need for recognition to be met, Josephat et al. (2021). Teachers are key elements in the development of any society but their status remains very low. They are looked upon by the society as downtrodden who are at least in the strata of the society. The society celebrates the so called highly place professions like medicine, law and forget about the dissemination of the knowledge to acquire the skill or certificate being celebrated. Before now, it was not like that but as a result of some factors such as huge number of teachers compared with other professions in Nigeria because Teacher Training Schools are seen as dumping ground for those students who could not make it to study better courses in the university.

Duodu (2001) on human relations theory upholds that the attention paid to workers and their involvement in activities of the organization could bring about increased productivity on the role of educational administrators. The managers of educational institutions are educational administrators who need good management techniques to carry out their tasks, encourage harmony in order to ensure effective performance. Recognition assists workers feel that their organization cherish them and their contributions to the uplift of the company and individual member. This is very important when organizations grow. It helps workers have a sense of security in their worth to the organization, and thereby motivate them to put in their utmost in achieving the set goal of their workplace. It has been found to be one of the strongest factors influencing job satisfaction of employees, Jun et al. (2006).

Influence of Professional Development on Teachers' job performance and satisfaction

Training is a systematic and planned process intended to improve the behaviour, attitude, knowledge and skills through learning experience in order to achieve effective and efficient job performance of employees. Its purpose is to develop the capacities of the individuals in order to satisfy both the present and future needs of an organization, Milhem et al. (2014). In-service teacher training is an essential aspect of staff development, it is a programme which is designed for teachers who are already in service. Its purpose is to improve their effectiveness, increase productivity, bring greater confidence in teachers and enrich their knowledge. It includes all professional development programmes which teachers participate in after early certificate obtained and tender for employment, it is a continuous process till retirement, Margaret et al. (2021). Training as an important aspect of staff development used mainly for the purpose of improving the performance of individual staff with assigned job responsibilities. It is used to develop a sense of purpose, widen the staff perception and increase the capacity to acquire knowledge and mastery of technical know-how. This is often done through orientation, career development, in-service training, refresher courses, and other activities in which a serving staff may participate for the purpose of extending his/her professional knowledge and skills (Ndukwu and Edo, 2020). Continuous Training of staff is the most crucial resource for organization to develop. Therefore, it is important that regular training should be encouraged to renew employees' interest in undertaking tasks effectively, as this motivates individual workers to get committed to the ideals of the organization.

Providing opportunities for professional development of teachers is an effective strategy that can be employed to attract and retain them in the profession. This may include workshops, training sessions, seminars, and other opportunities to learn new skills and stay up to date on the latest teaching methods and technologies. Edo et al. (2018) emphasized that school development should be aimed at improving the capabilities of teachers to perform various duties, responsibilities, and functions that are associated with their present or future expected roles. This involves increase in knowledge, skills and the development of positive attitude to work for enhancement of productivity and quality services. One of such professional development programs for teachers is the Train-the-Trainer (TTT) program which is a practical course that gives experienced teachers the opportunity to develop their knowledge and skills to become teacher trainers. It permits teachers to update their expertise to turn out to be learning facilitators, which requires using a different teaching method modified for contemporary learning such as blended learning and enable learners to gain experience through the process. The TTT program is built on the idea that learning is not about teaching what to do but about learning how to discover a solution on your own. Learning facilitators guide and help learners to be independent and be able to learn on their own. The "Train-the-Trainer" program gives teachers the practical skills required to become skillful facilitators, giving them the tools and experience to develop methodologies, invent classroom activities, use diverse technology, and implement verbal and non-verbal communication skills. Overall, this program gives teachers the means to improve their own classroom experiences and find greater satisfaction in their roles, without changing jobs. In order to solve the challenges confronting a particular institution in terms of performance of the staff, training is very key because it is seen as the process of acquisition of skills, knowledge and necessary approaches needed to overcome such threat or challenge. Organizing in-service training for teachers from time to time is crucial in determining the extent to which an institution intends to achieve its academic goals, as it is motivational for purposes of realizing increased job performance.

Influence of working environment on Teachers' job performance and satisfaction

Working environment provides an atmosphere upon which work is done. It encompasses availability of working tools and equipment, enough working space for accomplishment of various purposes. Oftentimes, supervisors demand a lot of effort from subordinates in the implementation of their tasks without full consideration on how necessary tools and resources required for tasks is acquired or its availability, Ondigo (2011). Some workers lack adequate and conducive work space, this has led some to be operating briefcase offices. The work of Hesborne (2015) presented that workers in some mining industries in Athi River were subjected to dangerous working conditions as they were not provided with protective safety gadgets, the workers continuously inhaling current dust which they are not supposed to

inhale making their working environment hostile. This resulted in some of the workers suffering respiratory problems which implies that the working environment poses a challenge to their health. According to Maldrine et al. (2019) work environment has significant influence on job satisfaction of teachers. The research showed that improving the work environment in the schools would lead to improvements in teachers' job satisfaction. According to Toth et al. (2000) government must establish an environment where teachers feel highly motivated and respected. Working environment in this context is seen in term of conducive environment, quality, style of classrooms and offices, availability of teaching resources and as well as the state of the resources available. Okonkwo and Obineli (2011) said that inspired workplace will result in inspired workers and draws attention to the importance of work performance, the social relationships, quality, and style of buildings and offices.

Relationship between Teachers' job satisfaction and performance

Teachers' job satisfaction plays an important role in a bid to increase the quality of education all over the world today, because teachers are central in achieving educational objectives hence the need to motivate them cannot be over emphasized. They are the life-wire of all educational organization. According to Okeke (2011), school objectives and aims are unachievable without the persistent commitment of the teachers. In order to get them committed, motivation plays an important role, it enhances job satisfaction as well as increases productivity and also improve their performances which invariably translate to goal achievement in an efficient manner. When teachers are satisfied with their jobs, it become evident in the outstanding performance of their students, thus, great efforts must be made to make sure that they get utmost satisfaction with their job, Maldrine et al. (2019). Satisfaction implies happiness and a state of psychological feeling of contentedness as an outcome of need fulfilment. According to Aworemi et al. (2011), when workers are happy, they show more interest in their works, and thereby perform better. When teachers are satisfied with their job, it keep them in the profession and also improve their job delivery. This means that satisfied teachers will be committed to their job and hence contribute significantly to the improvement of students' academic performance and school effectiveness at large. Teachers' job satisfaction has been found to be an essential pointer leading to effectiveness in schools as its product, and quality of work delivery as an important indicator of effectiveness of a school, Hoy and Miskel (2001). Researchers have found out that both job satisfaction and motivation of teachers are vital interventions and assurances to quality teaching and high standards of academic performance at all levels and stages of education (Pilot, 2007; Ingwu and Ekefre, 2006; Aldermon, 2004; Ngada, 2003). There are several factors that affect job satisfaction most especially secondary school teachers in public schools. These factors depend on administrator of the school, a study conducted by Dinham and Scott (2000), found that teachers who had earned promotions in their schools were more satisfied with their job than un-promoted teachers. Satisfied teachers tends to be more productive, creative and committed to their duties. Poor performance of many secondary school students as evident in their performance in tertiary institutions in Nigeria today can be as result of dissatisfaction of teachers.

Every individual works primarily to earn money in order to cater for his needs, once the kind of work engaged in cannot support him/her and provide for his immediate needs, the job is consider worthless and there will always be a desire to seek for better job and the effort put in at getting optimal output will reduce. If there is increase in the income/salary, the energy put in at getting result and level of commitment to the work will be affected positively, leading to better performance. Therefore motivation and performance are very important factors in terms of school success and students' achievements. Previous studies on motivational strategies on teachers have shown that teachers by some kind of incentives are recognized as being effective. Incentives are often given in the form of money; it is seen as part of the reward system designed to reinforce behaviour and motivate teachers to work towards the achievement of goals and objectives of the institution Sheena and Melca (2020). There is relationship between job satisfaction and performance, some researchers had proposed that teachers' satisfaction is a forecast of their performance meaning that job satisfaction will contribute significantly to improving their job performance, (Wolomasi et al., (2019); Eliyana et al. (2019); Simatupang et al. (2017)). A way to improve teachers' performance is to motivate them in order to ensure that they are satisfied with their

jobs, job satisfaction had been seen as one of the factors that impact teachers' performance, Orbe et al., (2018).

Statement of the Problem

Educational system has been confronting with various challenges across the globe. These challenges vary from country to country. In Nigeria, various problems are confronting the three levels of education which are primary, secondary and tertiary education, these problems include poor funding by government, politicization, inadequate instructional materials, uncondusive environment for effective learning and teaching processes, poor teacher welfare, shortage of teachers, lack of continuous training for teachers, large class size as well as location of schools. These challenges left unattended to have led to decline in the quality of education as it is evident in the society today. One of the most important issues that must be addressed in schools is how to increase the quality of education in which teachers' performance and job satisfaction play crucial role, Ghavifekr and Pillai (2016). In order to increase teachers' performance, there must be strategies consciously put in place that will motivate them to perform which will invariably lead to being satisfied with their jobs. Teachers' job satisfaction reflect on their students' performance and lead to building a well-structured society.

Purpose Of The Study

The specific objectives of this project are to:

- identify key motivational factors that influence teachers' performance and job satisfaction.
- establish a relationship between motivation and teachers' performance in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State
- examine the effects of motivation on job satisfaction of teachers' in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State

Research Questions

- What are the key motivational factors that influence teachers' performance and job satisfaction?
- What is relationship between motivation and teachers' performance in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State?
- What are the effects of motivation on job satisfaction of teachers' in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State?

Significance of the Study

The following are the expected outcome of the work

- how motivation can encourage the performance of teachers and bring about job satisfaction which will enables them to effectively and efficiently discharge that duties
- arouse the interest of students in teaching profession in order to have adequately trained teachers in schools
- producing well-grounded graduate who can further their educational career in any part of the world without issue.

RESEARCH METHOD

Descriptive survey research design was adopted to collect data through well-structured questionnaires which were carefully filled by 150 public secondary school teachers within the target population. It is useful when collecting information about people's attitudes, opinions, habits or any of the variety of education or social issues and also useful in obtaining both quantitative and qualitative data. In Schott's (1999) opinion survey research helps to reveal issues, conditions and other situations that exist between specific events through orderly collection, analysis, interpretation and report of pertinent facts and information concerning an enterprise. The population consists of secondary school teachers in twenty one (21) selected public secondary schools in which three schools were randomly selected from each local government within Edo South Senatorial District, Edo State. After the data collection from the respondents, simple percentage was used as main statistical method of data analysis. The raw data were scrutinized by inspecting each piece of data in order to identify simple mistake arising from items that

were wrongly responded to and any blank spaces left un-responded to by the respondents. The formula is $\frac{N}{150} \times 100$. Where N is the number of respondents in a group.

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH QUESTION

Research Question I: *What are the key motivational factors that influence teachers' performance and job satisfaction?*

The researcher from the conceptual framework of the study identifies some motivational factors that may likely influence teachers' performance and which will translate to job satisfaction.

1. **Influence of salary structure on teachers' job performance and satisfaction**

Salary is the money paid to an employee for doing his job. When an employee is adequately paid, it brings out higher performance in him/her. High wages usually give workers sense of fulfilment apart from the enormous task to be performed.

Table 1: Influence of salary structure on teachers' job performance and satisfaction

S/No	Statement	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1.	Teachers are leaving the country because of low salary structure	130	86.67	12	8.00	8	5.33
2.	Is your pay commensurate with your work as a teacher?	7	4.67	141	94.00	2	1.33
3.	Does your pay as a teacher meet your needs?	20	13.33	124	82.67	6	4.00
4.	Do you agree that low income push a lot of teachers to engage in other things outside teaching?	144	96.00	6	4.00	0	0.00

Source: Field survey

The study findings revealed as presented in table 1 that their salaries do not meet their needs, this has led to some teachers leaving the country for a greener pasture where they can earn more income, 130(86.67%) respondents attested to that. Also low income has made some teachers who are still in the system to be engaged in other things that can earn them additional income. This definitely affects the effectiveness of their job performance.

2. **Influence of recognition on teachers' job performance and satisfaction**

Every individual want to be accepted and appreciated when relating with people. Teachers are key architects of knowledge and have always play a vibrant role in building the future of nations. It is thus important to hold them in high esteem and accord them with proper recognition among their counterpart in other profession.

Table 2: Influence of recognition on teachers' job performance and satisfaction

S/No	Statement	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1.	Do teaching gives you desired recognition and respect in the society?	54	36.00	92	61.33	4	2.67
2.	Job satisfaction on the part of teachers leads to effective and efficient teaching.	136	90.67	12	8.00	2	1.33
3.	The status of teachers has remained low among other professional bodies in Nigeria	129	86.00	17	11.33	4	2.67
4.	Do you think that improved status of teachers will arouse the interest of people into teaching profession?	143	95.33	5	3.33	2	1.33

Source: Field survey

From the result from the questionnaire presented in table 2; 92(61.33%) teachers out of the 120 teachers who responded to the questionnaire said the society has no regards for teaching profession. 129 (86%) confirmed that teacher's status has remained low among other professional bodies in Nigeria. This has a

way of demoralizing them and discouraging students from having interest in the profession as it is evident in the number of students in teachers training institutes across the country. The total number of 129 (95.33%) of the respondents affiliate lack of interest in teaching profession with low status of teachers. Nevertheless, if there is improvement on the status of teachers, motivated by giving them proper recognition in the society, a lot of people will be interested in the profession and once someone is motivated intrinsically, he will be satisfied doing the work and performance will be enhanced. A lot of people run away from teaching profession because of low status, nevertheless this research shows that improved status of teacher will encourage people into the profession thereby put an end to shortage of teachers being expressing as it reflected in this research; (68.00%) respondents said they lack teachers. Those who are there in the service of Edo State as teachers enjoying it because of the remuneration the immediate past government made available to them. The fear of people is “can it be sustained by this new administration”? Since over the years, there have been no continuity in the governance of Nigeria as a whole.

Influence of working environment on teachers’ job performance and satisfaction

Working Environment in this context is seen as a well-structured and equipped environment that encourages teaching and learning for effective outcome. An environment that provides an atmosphere in which work can be done with outmost ease and joy, setting of classrooms and offices well furnished with availability of teaching resources as well as the state of the resources available. A conducive workplace will by no small measure inspire workers and make them perform the assigned tasks effectively and efficiently without compromise.

Generally, people get motivated to their performance when their working environment is satisfactory.

Table 3: Influence of working environment on teachers’ job performance and satisfaction

S/No	Statement	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1.	Do you have conducive working environment?	38	25.33	103	68.67	9	6.00
2.	Do you have adequate Instructional materials for effective teaching in your school?	35	23.33	110	73.33	5	3.33

Source: Field survey

The respondents were asked to indicate the types of working conditions in their various schools and their responses were presented in table 3. From their responses 103 (68.67%) stated that they do not have a conducive working environment, while 38 (25.33%) mentioned that they have and 9(6.00%) could not decide the state of their working environment. 35 (23.33%) indicated that they do have adequate instructional materials, 110 (73.33%) said that do not have adequate instructional materials. This results shows that most public secondary schools in Edo State lack conducive working environment.

Influence of In-Service Training on Teachers Job Performance and satisfaction

The most difficult task to perform is the process of being educated, the level at which one stop learning is the level such person will remain and with no time, starts to be obsolete. It is also a process that consumes a lot of resources and time. In order to make teachers to perform better in their task of teaching most especially in this century where technology is taking over every facet of the world, effective teacher training is crucial to equip them with requisite knowledge and skills necessary for moulding a strong crop of young people with the capacity to positively change the society. In-service training for teachers is a professional developmental training for teachers who are already in the classroom. It helps to improve and update their knowledge, skills and introduces them to educational reform across the globe. It should be a continuous process from the first day till the day of retirement.

Table 4: Influence of In-Service Training on Teachers Job Performance and satisfaction

S/No	Statement	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1.	Do you think there is need for in-service training for teachers?	146	97.33	4	2.67	0	0.00
2.	Is students holidays adequate for teacher to rest and prepare for new term?	103	68.67	40	26.67	7	4.67
3.	Do you think teachers need leaves apart from students' holiday?	92	61.33	49	32.67	9	6.00
4.	Do teacher come to work during students' holidays?	92	61.33	48	32.00	10	6.67
5.	If teachers are allowed to go for leave, can it improve their performance?	112	74.67	25	16.67	13	8.67
6.	Teachers continual development will lead to effective and efficient delivery	147	98.00	3	2.00	0	0.00
7.	Can provision for professional development help in retaining teachers in Edo State?	138	92.00	11	7.33	1	0.67

Source: Field survey

The result of the questionnaire administered to the respondents is presented in table 4. It can be seen from table 4 that 146 (97.33%) out of the 150 respondents said there is need for in-service training for teachers, 4(2.67%) does not see reason for such training. For effective and efficient job performance by teachers 147(98.00%) of the respondents agreed that in-service training will motivate teacher to be effective and efficient in their performance. However, 11(7.33%) does not see in-service training as a means of retaining teacher in public schools in Edo state, while 138(92.00%) believed strongly that professional development of teachers will drastically reduce the rate at which teachers resigns or leaves teaching profession in the state.

Research Question II: *What is relationship between motivation and teachers' job performance in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State?*

This sub-section presents findings for the research questions that says: what is the relationship between motivation and teacher's job performance in public school in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State? To achieve this objective, the researcher asked if the teachers need motivation to discharge their duties and also asked if there is any correlation between motivation and their performances as teachers.

Table 5: Relationship between motivation and teachers' job performance

S/No	Statement	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1.	Do teachers need motivation to discharge their duties effectively?	141	94.00	8	5.33	1	0.67
2.	Is it true that motivation does not have any correlation with performance of teacher?	27	18.00	118	78.67	5	3.33
3.	Do you think teachers being motivated will have positive effect on the educational development of this state?	146	97.33	3	2.00	1	0.67

Source: Field survey

The responses of the respondents has presented in table 5 showed that for teachers to discharge their duties effectively there is need for them to be motivated. 141(94.00%) respondents stated that motivation and performance is crucial to teachers' job performance, also 118(78.67%) stated that there is correlation between motivation and performance of teachers, which will invariably have positive effects on the educational development of the state.

Research Question III: What are the effects of motivation on job satisfaction of teachers' in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State?

The researcher intends to validate the effects of motivation on job satisfaction of teachers in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State, to achieve this, the study speculated that it is when one is satisfied with his job that he will participate in other extra-curricular activities and thereby asked respondents whether being motivated can arouse the interest of teachers to participate in extra-curricular activities.

Table 6: Effects of motivation on job satisfaction

S/No	Statement	Yes	%	No	%	Undecided	%
1.	Can motivation arouse the interest of teachers to participate in extracurricular activities?	143	95.33	7	4.67	0	0.00
2.	Job satisfaction on the part of teachers leads to effective and efficient teaching.	136	90.67	12	8.00	2	1.33

Source: Field survey

The findings has presented in table 6 showed that 143(95.33%) of the respondents agreed that when they are motivated they will be willing to participate in any extracurricular activity. Also 136(90.67%) of the respondents stated that job satisfaction leads to effective and efficient teaching and learning process. This indicates that job satisfaction plays an important role in contributing to teachers' behaviours at their workplace. It results in increased commitment towards work, increased productivity, increased morale, and less intentions to quit.

DISCUSSION

The result of the research question one showed that factors like good salary structure, recognition, working environment and in-service training are some of the motivational factors that influence teachers' job performance and satisfaction. These findings are in agreement with the opinion of Ndukwu and Edo (2020) who said that the success of teachers are depended on the quality, competency and skillfulness generated through motivation which comes from various measures inform of training, recognition, salary, and good working conditions. For any organization or institution to attain success, employees' satisfaction with their jobs plays a key role, hence, they need to be motivated from time to time in order to fulfil their task and achieve the goals and objectives of the organization.

The result of research question two indicated that there is relationship between motivation and teacher job performance as it was evidence from their responses as represented in table 5 where majority of the respondents (teachers) said there is correlation between being motivated and their performance which will invariably have positive effects on the educational development of the state. This finding corroborates with the discovery of Setyo Riyanto et al (2017) that motivation has positive and significant effect on the performance of teachers. Thus, motivation and performance are very important influences in determining the success of any institution. Teachers' motivation is an important issue that enable them to give utmost responsibility to impart knowledge and skills to learners.

It could be inferred from the results of the research question three that motivation has effects on teachers' job satisfaction. For individual to participate fully with enthusiasm in extracurricular activities in any organization, such person must have derived maximum satisfaction in the job which will lead to effective an efficient performance as observed in the table 6 where 136 (90.67%) out of 150 respondents agreed that job satisfaction on the part of teachers leads to effective and efficient teaching. This finding is in consonant with the work of Adamu Margaret et al., (2020) which stated that various factors of motivation has greater influence on teachers' job satisfaction and that for teachers to be effective in the discharge of their duties, efforts must be made to satisfy their needs.

Job Performance and Satisfaction of teachers are highly unavoidable in any institution. They are determined by the extent of motivation received which will inspire them to put in their best in order to achieve the aims and objectives of the learning and teaching processes. Just as individual person have needs that are expected to be met so also teachers have various needs that continuously competing with one another. The responses from the respondents showed that their needs are not met, this has pushed a

lot of them to engage in other things outside teaching profession and some had left the profession in search for greener pasture. There is relationship between salary, job performance and satisfaction, employees attached more importance to money earned when it is able to cater for their needs. High paid employees perform better than low pay employees. No single human being wants to be looked down on, everybody need commendation and recognition. This research has shown that teachers are not given the desired recognition and respect in the society compare to other professions but if their statues improved, people will develop interest in the profession, which will eradicate the shortage of teachers being expressed in some of the schools. A satisfactory working environment encourages performance, if the needed tools are available to both teachers and learners, teaching and learning processes become enjoyable. Therefore, adequate instructional material and conducive working environment should be provided in schools across the Senatorial District. Effective training is very crucial to teachers' development and it is essential to equip them with requisite knowledge and skills for the purpose of improving their performance. Motivation and performance are important variables that determine the success of an organization. Average human being like to make progress and attain to the peak of their careers, therefore when such persons are given opportunities to develop it will definitely boost their performance and as well result in job satisfaction. The results of the study showed that teachers need to be extrinsically motivated through their salaries, proper recognition, given opportunities for professional development and having a conducive working environment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is concluded that job performance and satisfaction of teachers are highly depended on motivation by the teacher. Thus, factors such as good salary structure, proper recognition, good working environment, and in-service training should be adequately used to increase job performance and satisfaction of teachers in Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Some teachers would have loved to remain in the profession and be more committed to the discharge of their duties if they are well paid, good salary structure should be prepared and paid alongside other benefits which their counterparts from various discipline are enjoying.
2. A lot of teachers are not proud to be called so because of low self-esteem among other professionals in Nigeria, therefore proper recognitions should be given to teachers.
3. Training should be organized for the teachers from time to time to enhance their capacity, improve their skills in teaching and learning processes.
4. Teachers should be encouraged to always further their academic careers and be trained in the utilization of modern technological instructional materials.
5. Conducive environment for learning and teaching with relevant instructional materials should be provided to enhance performance and satisfaction
6. Leave is important for teacher development because (61.33% respondents admitted that they come to school during holidays for administrative duties which make such period not suitable for them to go for developmental training) and 74.67% respondent said if teachers were allowed to go on leave it will improve their performance, therefore in order to enhance the performance of teacher which has positive impact on teaching/learning process, authority should look into the area of allowing teacher to go on leave. Holidays should be mainly for rest and preparations for new term/session.
7. Government and the educational stakeholders should recruit more teacher in the service of Edo South Senatorial District of Edo State

REFERENCES

- Adamu Margaret Ijaguwa, Ezekiel Ivagher Dondo and Rosemary Mulebee Asen (2020) Influence of Motivation on Secondary School Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Benue South Senatorial District, Nigeria BSUJEM. 2(1): 175 – 183

- Adamu Mohammed and Garba Waziri El-Jajah (2019). Payment of Teachers' Salary and Promotion as Correlate of Teachers' Job Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Adamawa State. Nigeria International Journal of Philosophy and Social-Psychological Sciences 5 (4): 39-46
- Aworemi JR, Abdul-Azeez IA, Durowoju ST, others (2011) An empirical study of the motivational factors of employees in Nigeria. *Int J Econ Finance* 3(5):227–233
- Bell, B. (2012). A summary of motivation theories' (pp. 1-26). Retrieved from <http://www.yourcoach.be/blog/wp-content/uploads/2012/03/A-summary-of-motivation-theories1.pdf>
- Brandmiller C, Dumont H, Becker M (2020) Teacher perceptions of learning motivation and classroom behavior: the role of student characteristics. *Contemp Educ Psychol*63:101893
- Businge, C. (2011). Uganda: Death, resignations eating into teachers. *The New Vision*, 17 August. Retrieved from <http://allafrica.com/stories/201108180900.ht>
- Dinham, S., & Scott, C. (2000). Moving into the Third Outer Domain of Teacher Satisfaction. *Journal of Education Administration*, 38, 379-396.
- Duodu, F. W. K. (2001). *The School Administrator*. Kumasi: SOSFAC (Gh.) Ltd
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN). (2013). *National policy on education 4th edition*. Lagos. NERDC press.
- Hesborne Nyakongo Ombuya (2015) Influence of Motivation on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Rachuonyo South Sub - County, Homa-Bay County Kenya
- Hoy, W.K., & Miskel, C.G. (2001). *Educational administration: Theory research and practice 6th (ed.)*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Igbafe K. R. and Ogonor B. O. (2019). Effect of Age, Marital Status, Gender and Professional Experience on Teachers' Work Motivation in Edo State Public Secondary Schools. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)* , vol. 9, no. 5, 2019, pp. 53-59
- Ingwu, E.U., & Ekefre, E.N. (2006). A Framework for measurement of teacher productivity in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Education Philosophy*, 2(2), 1-1
- Josephat Onyiego Orina, John Kanjogu Kiumi and Peter Kaboro Githae (2021). Recognition as a Determinant of Teacher Motivation in Public Secondary Schools in Kwale County, Kenya. *Review of Education Studies* 2770-9779: 1(1)
- Jun, M., Cai, S., & Shin, H. (2006). TQM practice in a maquiladora: Antecedents Journal of Teacher Education and Educators 26 of employee satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Operations Management*, 24, 791-812
- Junhao Fang (2023) Application and Limitations of the Expectancy Theory in Organizations. *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Financial Technology and Business Analysis*.
- Kayode, G. (2012). Nigeria: Beyond distribution of free textbooks. *Daily Trust*, 15 June. Retrieved from <http://allafrica.com/stories/201206150663.html>
- Komolafe, F. (2010). Teachers carpet government over rot in education. *Vanguard*, 24 June. Retrieved from <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2010/06/teachers-carpet-govtover-rotin-education/>
- Maldrine Tallam, Henry K. Kiplangat, Betty Tikoko (2019). Influence of the Work Environment on Job Satisfaction among Public Secondary School Teachers in Nakuru West Sub County, Kenya. *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development* 8(11):79 – 84
- Mary A (2010) Motivation and the performance of primary school teachers in Uganda: a case of Kimaanya-Kyabakuza division, Masaka District.
- Mbwana, D.M. (2015). *Motivation and Performance of Secondary School Teachers in Tanzania: A Case of Selected Secondary Schools in Mzumbe Ward, Mvomero District*. Dissertation.
- Milhem Wajdi, Abushamsieh Khalil and Aróstegu Maria Nieves Pérez (2014). Training Strategies, Theories and Types. *Journal of Accounting – Business & Management* 21(1): 12 – 26
- Mustafa, M., & Othman, N. (2010). The effect of work motivation on teacher's work performance in Pekanbaru senior high schools, Riau province, Indonesia. *Sosiohumanika*, 3(2), 259-272.

- Nadeem, M., Rana, M., Lone, A., Maqbool, S. Naz, K., and Ali, A. (2011). Teachers Competencies and factors affecting the performance of female Teachers in Bahawalpur (southern Punjab) Pakistan. *International. Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(19), 1-6.
- Ndukwu, Nkechinyer Rofifah Precious and Edo, Barineka Lucky (2020) Influence of Motivation on Teachers' Job Performance in Secondary Schools, Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology & Social Development* 8(3):105-111
- Ngada, J.A. (2003). Challenges and future of teacher education in Nigeria. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Research Development. National Universities Commission: VIHEP Information Booklet* (2003-2004).
- Nurun Nabi IM, Dip TM, H AA (2017) Impact of motivation on employee performances: a case study of Karmasangs than bank Limited, Bangladesh *Arab J Bus Manag Rev* 7(293):2
- Ogbonna, F. I. (2014). Teacher motivation: A factor for classroom effectiveness and school improvement in Nigeria. *College student Journal*, 38(2), 82-108.
- Okeke, D. (2011). *Quality management and nation goal attainment in education: the case of Nigeria*. Port Harcourt: University Press
- Okonkwo, M.C. and Obineli S.A. (2011). The Roles of counselling in promoting good leadership: Anambra state on the focus. *Review of Behavioural Sciences (JRBS)*, 3(1), 144-153
- Rofifah S, Sirojuddin A, Maarif MA, Zuana MMM (2021) The influence of organizational culture and work motivation on teacher performance at the international standard school, Amanatul Ummah Mojokerto. *Nidhomul Haq* 6(1):27-40
- Setyo Riyanto , Adonia and Hapzi Ali (2017) Effect of Motivation and Job Satisfaction on the Performance of Teachers in Mentari School Bintaro (MSB). *Scholars Bulletin (A Multidisciplinary Journal)* 3(1): 83 – 91
- Shaikh SH, Shaikh S, others (2019): The impact of extrinsic motivation on employees' performance: a case study of food industries in Sindh, Pakistan. *Am Sci Res J Eng Technol Sci* 56(1):26-37
- Sheena Mae Trestiza Comighud, Melca Jamio Arevalo (2020): Motivation In Relation To Teachers' Performance *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 10 (4), 1007
- Tasya IA, Gilang A (2020): The influence of motivation on employee's performance. *Almana* 4(2):262-265
- Toth SL, Cicchetti D, Macfie J, Rogosch FA, Maughan A (2000) Narrative representations of moral-affiliative and conflictual themes and behavioral problems in maltreated preschoolers. *J Clin Child Psychol* 29(3):307-318
- Wolomasi, A.K., Asaloei, S.I., Werang, B.R. (2019): Job satisfaction and performance of elementary school teachers. *Int. J. Eval. Res. Educ.* 8(4), 575-580